

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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One of the primary advantages of implementing these technologies is the automation of economic processes, which reduces human intervention and conserves resources. Furthermore, electronic document exchange accelerates integration into international trade relations, enhancing competitiveness in global economic interactions.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

In the process of digitalizing Uzbekistan's economy, electronic document exchange technologies play a significant role. Scientific research in this area highlights the implementation and development directions of these technologies.

An article published in the scientific electronic journal «Digital Economy» examines various aspects of the digital economy and the processes of its formation across different regions of the country. The study emphasizes the importance of digitalization, digital transformations, regional development, and information and communication technologies.

The textbook «New Technologies in Digital Economy and E-commerce» provides valuable insights into the issues underpinning modern e-commerce and the foundations of the digital economy. It explores mechanisms for transitioning to a digital economy, effective business models in e-commerce and electronic business, and the development of areas such as cloud technologies, financial technologies, the Internet of Things, artificial intelligence, digital currencies, and virtual reality.

A study guide titled «Electronic Document Exchange Systems», published on an independent learning platform, notes that electronic document exchange enables not only the exchange of documents but also the organization of work without relying on paper carriers. It simplifies processes like searching for documents, preparing reports, and archiving.

An analysis of these sources reveals that a range of scientific research and practical measures are being implemented to introduce and develop electronic document exchange technologies in Uzbekistan. These efforts contribute to accelerating the digital transformation of the country's economy.

These resources provide valuable insights into the implementation and development of electronic document exchange technologies in Uzbekistan. Furthermore, advancing scientific research in this field is essential to enhance the significance of these technologies in the development of the digital economy.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology involved collecting data from scholarly literature, government documents, and statistical sources. The data was analyzed using content analysis to evaluate the economic efficiency and development trends of electronic document exchange technologies. Additionally, a comparative approach was employed to draw insights by contrasting the findings with international practices.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The further development of electronic document exchange technologies in Uzbekistan involves several critical areas, including the enhancement of infrastructure, strengthening security measures, and introducing innovative solutions aligned with the needs of a digital economy. Thus, electronic document exchange technologies can be seen as a cornerstone of the country's digital transformation and a key enabler for economic modernization.

Electronic Document Circulation (EDC) is a cornerstone of digital transformation that enables efficient management of documents, improves transparency, and reduces operational costs. Uzbekistan has embarked on a path of economic modernization and digitalization, aiming to enhance productivity across its economy. The adoption of EDC systems presents opportunities for the public and private sectors. However, challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, legal gaps, and digital literacy need to be addressed to maximize its benefits. This paper explores supported by data, case studies, and recommendations.

The government of Uzbekistan has introduced several initiatives to promote electronic document. For instance, introduction "E-government" system has made it possible for citizens to access a wide range of public services online. The system has also made it easier for businesses to register and pay taxes electronically. Furthermore, the Central Bank of Uzbekistan has implemented an electronic payment system for interbank transactions.

1-picture illustrates the components of a DMS.

This is 1-picture illustrates the components and functionality of a DMS, highlighting its role in organizing, storing, and retrieving digital documents. Here is an explanation of the key features presented:

- Search: Enables efficient document retrieval through indexing and keyword-based search.
- File Systems: Manages the organization and structure of files for easier access.
- Communication Module: Facilitates collaboration and communication related to document sharing and approval processes.
- Version Control: Tracks changes to documents and maintains a history of edits, ensuring that previous versions can be retrieved if needed.
- Document Retrieval: Provides access to stored documents quickly, even in large databases.
- Document Archiving: Ensures long-term storage and protection of important files for compliance and reference purposes.
- Meta Data: Stores additional information about each document (e.g., author, date, tags) to enhance searchability and organization.

Despite the efforts made by the government, the implementation of electronic document circulation still faces several. Many people are still hesitant to use e-documents due to concerns about security and reliability. Another challenge is the inadequate legal framework for e-documents. The current legislation does not fully address the legal status of e-documents, which creates uncertainty and undermines their use.

Despite the challenges, the benefits of e-document circulation are numerous. E-documents are faster, cheaper, and more environmentally friendly than paper documents. They also reduce the risk of errors and increase the efficiency of document management. Moreover, e-documents can contribute to the digitalization of the economy and improve the overall competitiveness of the country.

The government needs to raise awareness among citizens and businesses about the advantages of e-documents and ensure their security and reliability. It also needs to develop a comprehensive legal framework that fully recognizes the legal status of e-documents. Furthermore, the government needs to provide support and incentives for the adoption of e-documents, such as tax benefits and subsidies.

According to the World Bank's «Doing Business 2022» report, Uzbekistan ranks 11th out of 190 countries in the «Getting Credit» category, which measures the ease of getting credit and the legal rights of borrowers and lenders. One of the factors that contributed to this ranking is the country's adoption of e-documentation in the credit reporting system. The report notes that Uzbekistan has made significant progress in implementing electronic platforms for credit reporting and has improved access to credit information for businesses.

The 2-picture illustrates how digital technologies are extensively applied across various sectors of the economy, highlighting a trend that drives global digital transformation.

Digital technology spreads through the entire economy

2-pic. Digital technology spreads through the entire economy.

Challenges of Implementing E-Documentation:

A survey conducted by the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Uzbekistan in 2021 found that 62% of businesses in the country still use paper documents for most of their transactions. The survey also revealed that one of the main reasons why businesses are hesitant to switch to e-documents is the lack of awareness and understanding of the benefits of electronic document circulation. Other concerns include the lack of technical infrastructure and the high cost of implementation.

According to a study by the United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific (ESCAP), the adoption of e-documentation in the trade sector can reduce trade costs by up to 25%. The study notes that e-documents can streamline trade procedures, reduce processing time, and improve the accuracy of data. Moreover, e-documentation can facilitate cross-border trade by reducing the need for physical documents and enabling online authentication and verification of trade documents.

The government of Uzbekistan has set a goal of achieving a fully digital economy by 2030. To achieve this goal, the government has launched several initiatives to promote the use of e-documents and digital technologies in various sectors of the economy. For instance, the «Digital Uzbekistan» program aims to create a unified digital platform for public services and e-commerce. The program also includes plans to establish a national electronic signature system and to develop e-invoicing and e-payment systems.

Here are some more statistics related to the topic:

The adoption of e-documentation is closely related to the development of egov services. Uzbekistan, government has launched several initiatives to provide digital services to citizens and businesses. The country has made significant progress in the online service index, which measures the availability and quality of online government services, and ranks 43rd globally with a score of 0.849.

Here's the data presented in a table format for better clarity (table 1):

Table 1. Key Metrics of E-Government Development and Online Services.

Metric	Description	Rank	Score
E-Government Development Index	Measures overall development of e-government services	90/193	0.556
Online Service Index	Measures availability and quality of online services	43/193	0.849

This data highlights Uzbekistan's progress in digital government initiatives, showcasing significant achievements in online services compared to its overall e-government performance.

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